

Paper 46**A CRITICAL STUDY ON APPLICATIONS OF
MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS IN BUSINESS
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Abstract:

The advancement of Information and Communication Computing Technology (ICCT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) made a revolution in Computer Science and its applications areas like Business Intelligence (BI). Artificial Intelligence, Business Intelligence, and Machine Learning work together in order to predict and analyze some complex business analytics and thereby assisting the top managers to take some better decisions at higher levels. With the aid of Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning can able to provide the ability to machines or systems automatically learn, and take decisions like human beings without programming explicitly based on experience. Machine Learning concepts have applications in diverse fields like day-to-day or daily business transactions to complex business analytics like Marketing Analytics, Pricing Analytics, Social Media Analytics, Customer Analytics, Supply Chain Analytics, and many more. Business Analytics is analyzing the business in 3600 angle which covers historical perspective or Descriptive, future perspective or Predictive and combinations of both or Perspective in order to make better and highly valuable decisions. Machine learning algorithms include supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and Meta-learning. The Machine learning algorithms include different techniques like Nearest Neighbour, Naive Bayes, Decision Tree, Classification Rule, Regression Analysis, Regression Trees, Neural Networks, Support Vector Machines, and many others. Unsupervised learning includes Clustering, Anomaly Detection, Association Rule, and a few others. Meta-learning algorithm covers Bagging, Boosting, Random Forest and a few others. This paper covers applications of machine learning algorithms in different areas of business analytics which includes Marketing Analytics, Pricing Analytics, Social Media Analytics, Customer Analytics, Supply Chain Analytics, Healthcare Analytics, and Portfolio analytics. This paper also tries to distinguish between supervised learning and unsupervised learning. This paper tries to find upcoming areas where machine learning algorithms can best fit in order to make some complex decision or to solve complex business problems.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence, Neural Network, Supervised Learning, Unsupervised Learning, Business Analytics, Meta-Learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Data is the centered around all types of business analytics which acts as raw input and are generated every now and then from various sources. Human beings are centered around this data and can generate data through different activities like mobile usage and computing,

health care, professional, entertainment, pricing, financial, social media, sports, retail and many more [1]. Not only human beings but also machine generates data like robotics systems, satellite system, computers, and an other types of machine which are used by human beings for various purposes all over the world. Data are usually classified as structured, semi structured, quasi-structured and un-structured data and spread over the globe [2]. The structured data are usually stored in well defined format and are easily recorded, where as unstructured data are not having any order and schema which are generating using various click streams at the time of browsing and internet usage [3-4]. Larger and unstructured or schema less data are accessible at our fingertips through internet. The machine learning is the special field where heterogeneous data are processed into information using well defined set of algorithms and these informations are used for business intelligent decision making purpose. The machine learning field is closely related with statistics, mathematical techniques, and computer science or computing power [5]. Due to mobile wireless technology, satellite, internet of things, and many more advanced technology created data explosions and which necessitated need of extra or more computing power and that led to the development of more statistical methods to discover and analyze the huge datasets.

A closely related branch of machine learning, data mining, deals with the generation of new knowledge from large databases [6]. As the name implies, data extraction involves a systematic search for a piece of actionable intelligence. While there is some disagreement about the extent to which machine learning and data extraction overlap, a possible point of distinction is that machine learning focuses on teaching computers how to use data to solve a problem, while Data extraction focuses on teaching computers to identify patterns that humans then use to solve a problem. Practically all data extraction involves the use of machine learning, but not all machine learning involves data extraction [7-9]. For example, you can apply machine learning to car traffic data from the data mine for patterns related to accident rates; On the other hand, if the computer is learning to drive the car itself, this is purely machine learning without data mining. Machines are not good at asking questions, or even knowing what questions to ask. They are much better at answering them, provided the question is stated in a way the computer can comprehend. Present-day machine learning algorithms partner with people much like a bloodhound partners with its trainer; the dog's sense of smell may be many times stronger than its master's, but without being carefully directed, the hound may end up chasing its tail [10].

This paper is divided into five sections. Section1 describes brief introduction to machine learning, data explosion, and machine learning and data mining. Section 2 describes types of data and learning. Section 3 describes business analytics types. Section 4 describes machine learning applications. Section 5 concludes the paper. This paper also tries to distinguish between supervised learning and unsupervised learning. This paper tries to find upcoming areas where machine learning algorithms can best fit in order to make some complex decision or to solve complex business problems.

2. TYPES OF DATA AND LEARNING

Digital data can be broadly classified into structured, semi-structured and unstructured data [11-13].

Unstructured data: data that does not fit a data model or is not in a form that can be easily used by a computer program. About 80-90% of the data of an organization is in this format; For example, notes, chat rooms, PowerPoint presentations, images, videos, letters, research, technical documents, the body of an email, etc [14]. Unstructured data does not fit any

predefined data model. In fact, to explain things a bit more, let's take a closer look at the different types of text available and the possible structure associated with it. In general, the structure or framework of unstructured data is quite unpredictable. In Figure 1.8 we look at the other sources of unstructured data. Essentially everything that has not been specifically structured is considered unstructured. The list of truly unstructured data includes free text, such as documents produced in your company, images and videos, audio files and some types of social networks. If the object to be stored does not carry labels (metadata about the data) and does not have an established scheme, ontology, glossary or consistent organization, it is not structured. However, in the same category as unstructured data, there are many types of data that have at least one organization. Some more examples of unstructured data are Twitter messages, Facebook posts, log files and email. Nowadays, unstructured data constitutes approximately 80% of the data that is generated in any company. The balance is clearly changing in favor of unstructured data. It is such a large percentage that it can not be ignored. *Semi-structured data*: data that does not fit a data model but has some structure. However, it is not in a form that can be easily used by a computer program; for example, emails, XML, markup languages such as HTML, etc. The metadata for this data is available but not sufficient. Semi-structured data is also known as a self-description structure. It has the following characteristics:

1. It does not conform to the data models that one usually associates with relational databases or any other form of data tables.
2. Use labels to segregate semantic elements.
3. Labels are also used to impose hierarchies of records and fields within the data.
4. There is no separation between the data and the scheme. The amount of structure used is dictated by the purpose in question.
5. In semi-structured data, entities belonging to the same class and also grouped do not necessarily have to have the same set of attributes. And, in any case, they have the same set of attributes, the order of the attributes may not be similar and, for all practical purposes, it is not important either.

Structured data: are the data that are organized (for example, in rows and columns) and that a computer program can easily use. Relationships exist between data entities, such as classes and their objects. The data stored in databases is an example of structured data. The majority of the structured data is maintained in RDBMS. An RDBMS conforms to the relational data model in which the data is stored in rows / columns. The number of rows / records / tuples in a relationship is called the cardinality of a relation and the number of columns is known as the degree of a relation. The current data store contains structured data and only structured data. It is structured because when it was placed in its relational database system a structure was imposed, so we know where it is, what it means and how it relates to other data there. It can be text (the name of a person) or numeric (its age) but we know that the value of age goes with a specific person, therefore structured. If your data is highly structured, you can look at it using any of the available RDBMS. It is normally used to maintain transaction / transaction data generated and collected by daily business activities. In other words, data from Online Transaction Processing (OLTP) systems are generally quite structured.

The learning can be classified into two types as supervised learning and unsupervised learning.

Supervised Learning: A predictive model is used for tasks that involve, as the name implies, the prediction of a value using other values in the data set. The learning algorithm attempts to discover and model the relationship between the objective characteristic (the characteristic that is predicted) and the other characteristics. Despite the common use of the word "prediction" to imply forecasting, predictive models do not necessarily need to predict events in the future. For example, a predictive model could be used to predict past events, such as the date of conception of a baby using the mother's current hormonal levels. Predictive models can also be used in real time to control the traffic lights during peak hours. Because predictive models receive clear instructions about what they need to learn and how they should learn it, the process of training a predictive model is known as supervised learning. Supervision does not refer to human participation, but to the fact that objective values provide a way for the student to know how well he has learned the desired task. Stated more formally, given a data set, a supervised learning algorithm attempts to optimize a function (the model) to find the combination of characteristic values that result in the objective result. In the classification, the destination characteristic to be predicted is a categorical characteristic known as the class, and it is divided into categories called levels. A class can have two or more levels, and the levels may or may not be ordinal. Because classification is used so much in machine learning, there are many types of classification algorithms, with appropriate strengths and weaknesses for different types of input data.

Supervised trainees can also be used to predict numerical data such as income, laboratory values, test scores or item counts. To predict such numerical values, a common form of numerical prediction adjusts the linear regression models to the input data. Although regression models are not the only type of numerical models, they are by far the most used. Regression methods are widely used for forecasting, since they quantify in exact terms the association between the inputs and the objective, including both, the magnitude and uncertainty of the relationship.

Unsupervised Learning: A single feature is more important than any other. In fact, because there is no objective to be learned, the process of training a descriptive model is called unsupervised learning. Although it may be more difficult to think of applications for descriptive models, after all, the good thing is that a student, who is not learning anything in particular, is used quite frequently for data extraction.

For example, the descriptive modeling task called pattern discovery is used to identify useful associations within the data. Pattern discovery is often used to analyze the market basket in the transactional purchase data of retailers. Here, the goal is to identify items that are often bought together, so that the information learned can be used to refine marketing tactics. For example, if a retailer finds out that swim trunks are commonly purchased at the same time as sunglasses, the retailer may reposition items more closely at the store or perform a promotion to "sell" to customers with associated articles.

The descriptive modeling task of dividing a data set into homogeneous groups is called clustering. This is sometimes used for segmentation analysis that identifies groups of individuals with similar behavior or demographic information, so that ad campaigns could be tailored to particular audiences. Although the machine is capable of identifying groups, human intervention is required to interpret them. For example, given five different groups of buyers in a grocery store, the marketing team should understand the differences between the groups to create the promotion that best suits each group.

Finally, a class of machine learning algorithms known as meta-apprentices is not tied to a specific learning task, but focuses on learning to learn more effectively. A meta-learning algorithm uses the results of some learning to inform the additional learning. This can be beneficial for very difficult problems or when the performance of a predictive algorithm should be as accurate as possible.

3. BUSINESS ANALYTICS TYPES

The different types of business analytics are Marketing Analytics, Pricing Analytics, Social Media Analytics, Customer Analytics, Supply Chain Analytics, and many more. Business Analytics is analyzing the business in 360° angle which covers historical perspective or Descriptive, future perspective or Predictive and combinations of both or Perspective in order to make better and highly valuable decisions [15].

Descriptive Analytics: Descriptive analyzes are performed to answer questions about events that have already occurred. This form of analysis contextualizes the data to generate information. Sample questions may include:

- What was the volume of sales in the last 12 months?
- What is the number of support calls received according to the category of severity and geographic location?
- What is the monthly commission that each sales agent earns?

It is estimated that 80% of the analytical results generated are descriptive in nature. In terms of value, descriptive analyzes provide the least value and require a relatively basic set of skills. Descriptive analytics is often done through ad-hoc reports or control panels. Reports are generally static in nature and show historical data that is presented in the form of data grids or graphs. Queries are executed in operational data stores from a company, for example, a customer relationship management system (CRM) or an enterprise resource planning system (ERP).

As an example, the descriptive analysis includes consulting the policy administration system to determine the number of policies sold each day, consulting the claims management system to find out how many claims are sent daily, and checking the billing system to find out how many customers are behind your premium payments.

Marketing Analytics: Marketing analysis includes the processes and technologies that allow marketers to evaluate the success of their marketing initiatives. This is achieved by measuring performance (for example, blogs versus social networks versus channel communications). Marketing analysis uses important business metrics, such as ROI, marketing attribution and marketing effectiveness in general. In other words, it tells you how your marketing programs are really working. Marketing analysis collects data from all marketing channels and consolidates them into a common marketing vision. From this common point of view, you can extract analytical results that can provide invaluable assistance to boost your marketing efforts.

Over the years, as companies expanded into new marketing categories, new technologies were adopted to support them. Because each new technology was usually implemented in isolation, the result was a mix of disconnected data environments. Consequently, marketing professionals often make decisions based on data from individual channels (for example, website metrics), regardless of the overall marketing image. The information of social networks alone is not enough. Web analytics data alone is not enough. And the tools that watch only one snapshot in time for a single channel are terribly inadequate.

Predictive Analytics: Predictive analysis is the use of data, statistical algorithms and machine learning techniques to identify the probability of future results based on historical data. The goal is to go beyond knowing what has happened to provide a better assessment of what will happen in the future. Although predictive analysis has existed for decades, it is a technology whose time has come. More and more organizations are turning to predictive analytics to increase their profitability and competitive advantage. Because right now?

- Growing volumes and types of data, and more interest in using data to produce valuable information.
- Faster and cheaper computers.
- Software easier to use.
- Tougher economic conditions and a need for competitive differentiation

As interactive and easy-to-use software is becoming more frequent, predictive analytics is no longer just the domain of mathematicians and statisticians. Business analysts and online business experts are also using these technologies.

Pricing Analytics: In marketing, price analysis refers to the analysis of consumer response to theoretical prices in survey research. In general, price analysis is the process of examining and evaluating a proposed price without evaluating its separate cost elements and the proposed profit / rate. The price analysis can also refer to the breakdown of a price into a unit figure. In general, per unit of price analysis, per square meter, square foot of accommodation, per hectare or even square meter of land. The price with the appropriate adjustment for several differences is applied to the valuation problem.

Financial Analytics: financial analysis is the creation of an ad hoc analysis to answer specific business questions and forecast possible future financial scenarios. The financial analysis software can accelerate the creation of reports and present the data in an executive panel, a graphical presentation that is easier to read and interpret than a series of spreadsheets with dynamic tables.

Social Media Analytics: The analysis of social networks is the practice of collecting data from social network websites and analyzing them using social network analysis tools to make business decisions. The most common use of social media analysis is to undermine customer confidence to support marketing and customer service activities.

Sports Analytics: Sports analytics are a broad spectrum that basically covers production in the field and outside of it, and how to obtain an advantage. It helps coaches by measuring opponents' tendencies, and helps GMs get a complete study of a player on and off the field, as well as how they fit in with other players on the team. It also helps in the creation of the playbook, in judging the strengths and weaknesses of a player, and how it can be correlated with better production.

4. MACHINE LEARNING APPLICATIONS

Although it is impossible to list all the use cases of machine learning, a survey of recent success stories includes several outstanding applications:

- Identification of unwanted spam messages in the email.
- Segmentation of customer behavior for targeted advertising.
- Predictions of climatic behavior and long-term climate changes.
- Reduction of fraudulent transactions with a credit card.
- Estimates Actuarial estimates of financial damages from storms and natural disasters.
- Prediction of popular electoral results.

- Development of algorithms for automatic piloting drones and automatic driving cars.
- Optimization of energy use in homes and office buildings.
- Projection of areas where criminal activity is most likely.
- Discovery of genetic sequences linked to diseases.

The ability of machines to understand the language has improved enough since 1994, so that Google, Apple and Microsoft have enough confidence to offer virtual concierge services operated through voice recognition. Even so, even these services routinely struggle to answer relatively simple questions. Furthermore, online translation services sometimes misinterpret phrases that a young child would easily understand. The predictive text function on many devices has also led to a series of sites with self-correcting errors with humor that illustrate the computer's ability to understand basic language but completely misinterpret the context.

5. CONCLUSION

The avalanche of data has led some to say that we have entered an era of Big Data, but this may be a bit inappropriate. Humans have always been surrounded by large amounts of data. What makes the current era unique is that we have large amounts of recorded data, many of which can be accessed directly from computers. The largest and most interesting data sets are increasingly accessible at the tip of our fingers, just a web search. This large amount of information has the potential to inform action, given a systematic way to make sense of all this. This paper divided into five sections. Section 1 described brief introduction to machine learning, data explosion, and machine learning and data mining. Section 2 described types of data and learning. Section 3 described business analytics types. Section 4 described machine learning applications. Section 5 concluded the paper. This paper also tries to distinguish between supervised learning and unsupervised learning.

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